

Proposed Marketing Strategy to Increase Brand Awareness of TMO

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ABSTRACT: The car population in Indonesia is increasing every year with an average of 4.8% in the last five years. The contribution of car population is dominated by passenger cars with a contribution of 74.5% when compared to commercial cars, so that this causes the lubricant industry for cars, especially passenger cars, is still survive and still one of the promising industries when viewed from the needs of the society. PT Toyota-Astra Motor (PT TAM), is a car trading company headquartered in North Jakarta, Indonesia. PT TAM sees an opportunity for this business by making special car lubricant products for the Toyota brand, namely TMO or Toyota Motor Oil. In Indonesia, the Toyota car brand is still the market leader with a market share of 33.3%. But unfortunately, there are still few people who know the TMO brand. This is reflected through a questionnaire that has been distributed by the authors to 255 respondents, and only 30% know the TMO brand. For this reason, the author is interested in researching more about proposed marketing strategies to increase brand awareness of TMO products. To be able to find out the right strategy, the author analyses the SWOT, STP, and also the marketing mix of TMO products. Then the author compiled a questionnaire that can provide market conditions related to TMO awareness, customer behaviour when buying engine oil products, customer behaviour when changing oil products, and customer priorities. After conducting an analysis through a questionnaire distributed to 255 respondents and interviews with speakers from PT TAM, namely the marketing team, product development team, and pricing team, the author describes the SWOT analysis, describe the STP proposal, and marketing strategy based on the AIDA framework. AIDA stands for attention, interest, desire, and action. The author designed a marketing strategy based on the AIDA framework.

KEYWORDS: Brand Awareness, Car Lubricants, Marketing Strategy, STP, and AIDA Framework

INTRODUCTION

The Association of Indonesian Automotive Industries, or GAIKINDO as it is more commonly known, reports that wholesale car sales increased by 7.3% between 2015 and 2018, even though there were declines of 17.7% in 2019 and 48.3% in 2020 as a result of the Covid-19 pandemic [1]. However, in 2021, with an increase of 66.7% units, the value began to recover. The contribution of the passenger cars, which include sedans, two-wheel drives, four-wheel drives, and low-cost green car types, to the wholesales automobile is more than that of commercial vehicles like pick-up, truck, bus, and double cabin types. The market for lubricating goods, particularly motor oil, is still very large. This occurred because the annual growth in car sales is directly correlated with the demand growth for engine oil. Even while wholesale cars are becoming less valuable, the need for engine oil keeps rising because it needs to be changed every 10,000 kilometers or 6 months. There are several well-known vehicle brands in Indonesia. For the past few years, Toyota, one of the automakers, has dominated the market. Toyota had a 33,3% market share in 2021 [2]. The largest in the ASEAN region, Indonesia has the highest annual use of lubricants, at 987 million liters [3]. Toyota Motor Oil (TMO) as the lubricant product of Toyota, from 2015-2020, had the average achievement of 13,4 million liters per year. This indicates that the TMO percentage of total engine oil usage is merely 3.2%. PT Pertamina Lubricants continues to dominate the market for lubricant goods with a 58% market share [4]. The market share of Toyota from the previous section, which previously dominated the 33,3% of the market in Indonesia, is in contrast to the fact that TMO only controls 3,2% of the market. TMO, the engine oil created specifically by the Toyota Manufacturing Corporation (TMC) for Toyota vehicles, is thought to have a greater market share potential than its rivals. TMO, however, continues to be left off of the list of TOP Brand Award surveys, and its share of the Indonesian engine oil market was only 3,2%. Because of this, the author is interested in examining TMO's present marketing plan and suggesting the best one to raise the company's brand awareness.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Marketing

Marketing is the process of creating, conveying, delivering, and exchanging value-added products and services for consumers,

clients, partners, and society at large [5]. Marketing's definition is that its purpose is to identify and cater to social and personal requirements. Companies must be able to modify their products in order for the market to benefit from them.

Segmentation, Targeting, and Positioning

Segmentation, Targeting, and Positioning popularly known as STP. STP formula is the essence of strategic marketing. A market segment is a collection of customers who have similar demands and expectations [5]. There are several elements of segmentation, which are filtered by geographic, demographic, psychographic, and behavioral. Meanwhile, market targeting is the process of examining and selecting certain market sectors. On the other hand, positioning is the process of tailoring a company's offering and image to stand out in the minds of its target market

Marketing Mix

The marketing mix refers to the strategies or marketing activities that use to meet consumer needs and effectively place our offering in their minds, which involves the 7Ps. 7Ps consist of Product, Price, Place, Promotion, People, Process, and Physical Evidence [5].

Brand Awareness

Figure 1. Brand Awareness Pyramid

Consumers become aware of a brand when they become aware that it exists. According to theory, there are a number of crucial components to measuring brand awareness, including brand recall, brand recognition, and top of mind [6]. Consumers who are uninformed of a brand are at the base of the brand awareness pyramid, or unaware of a brand. Brand recall measures a consumer's ability to remember which brands, out of several, come to mind when posed a question concerning a certain product category. When you aid customers in identifying brands in a specific category by discussing the qualities of the company's product brand while they are asking inquiries, you are demonstrating your brand recognition skills. Lastly, top of mind is when a customer is asked an unprompted question about a category, it has the connotation of the first brand that comes to mind.

AIDA Framework

Figure 2. AIDA Framework

There is a well-known marketing framework for increasing brand awareness, developing sales, and marketing communication plans which is called the AIDA framework [7]. The first stage is to secure attention. The primary goal of this stage is to raise brand awareness and attract buyers' attention to the offer. The second stage is to evoke interest. It's time to stimulate your customers' attention once they've heard about the brand, product, or service. The third stage is to stimulate desire. At this point, the company must convert the customer's curiosity into desire. The fourth stage is to initiate action. When customers have enough information about your product or service's brand, the business must encourage them to take action.

METHODOLOGY

Research methodology refers to a way for analyzing and explaining a research problem [8]. It's a methodical approach to research that might be regarded as a science of analysis. In order to answer the research questions, the data will be collected from the primary data and secondary data. The primary data will be collected by questionnaire and interview. The questionnaire will be distributed to the respondents who own a car and have used or purchased engine oil, both TMO or brands other than TMO. The author calculates the The estimated valid number of participants in the interview is between three to ten participants [9]. For this research, the interview will be conducted with three employees in PT TAM which are parts marketing and demand management team, parts development team, and parts pricing team. Meanwhile for secondary data, the data collections methodology that will be used by the author are PT TAM internal data, book literature, and article from website.

Conceptual Framework

This research's conceptual framework aims to analyze the current marketing strategy of TMO that is already conducted by PT TAM and also proposed the marketing strategy that related to the business issue of TMO. To analyze that, this research uses several tools such as Marketing Mix 7P's, STP, brand awareness evaluation, and AIDA framework.

Figure 3. Conceptual Framework

FINDING AND ARGUMENTS

SWOT Analysis

Strength, Weakness, Opportunities, and Threat is referred to as SWOT. a framework that enables management to develop strategic implications by fusing insights from assessments of opportunities and threats from the outside world with those from internal assessments of a company's strengths and weaknesses (S and W) [10]. Consequently, the company's internal strengths and weaknesses outweigh its exterior opportunities and threats.

Table 1. SWOT of TMO

Strength	Weakness
TAM as the Toyota cars and spare parts distributor company has a good brand image in the market. Represented by the 33,3% market share in 2021 is Toyota cars. TMO is formulated and approved by TMC, specially designed for Toyota cars. International standard and certified products. TMO has a variety of line up from mineral, synthetic, and full synthetic for the gasoline and diesel engine type. TMO has a very wide distribution network and distributors throughout Indonesia.	The price of TMO is higher than other big competitor brands such as Fastron, Shell, and Castrol. Lack of branding, which leads to low brand awareness of TMO. The TMO line up is not as complete as the competitors in the market. No TMO official store in e-commerce. Digitization tools have not been developed optimally.

Opportunity

Indonesia's market size for lubricant products, especially engine oil, is quite large. Toyota cars still dominate the market share in Indonesia. TMO can develop, improve, or complete the product specification to provide and fulfill the customer needs in the market. Educate the customer about the importance of using the genuine product and how to differentiate between the genuine and counterfeit product of TMO. Provide product knowledge to educate the customers so the customers understand what TMO specification that suits the best for their Toyota cars. The development of digital technology and ecommerce can be an opportunity to increase TMO's market share and make it easier for customers to access TMO products. Conduct branding to increase the brand awareness of TMO.

Threat

A lot of competitors in the market. Many brands offer interesting marketing promotions or programs that can attract the customers. In the market, many competitors have started to develop a lineup of oil with a thinner viscosity. High demand for engine oil can lead to an increasing TMO counterfeit products in the market. Nowadays, customers are able to easily access the information about the benefits, the weaknesses, the reviews about an engine oil product on the internet or social media, it will affect their decision when choosing engine oil.

Brand Awareness Evaluation

This section consists of questionnaire results from 255 respondents that can evaluate the customers' brand awareness towards car engine oil products. The questionnaire is construct by using the brand awareness pyramid:

1. Unaware Brand

This first stage indicates the level of customers' awareness about TMO. According to this data, from the total of 255 respondents there are 167 respondents (65,5%) that do not know the brand called TMO. 88 respondents (34,4%) from the total of 255 respondents are aware about TMO. The majority of them know about TMO from the Offline Marketplace such as authorized workshop or spare parts store with the total of 54 respondents (61,4%). However, even though they are aware of the TMO brand, only 47 respondents (53,4%) from the total of 88 respondents who are willing to purchase TMO as their engine oil product.

2. Brand Recognition

From 88 respondents who are aware of TMO, 7 respondents (8,0%) are strongly disagree, 10 respondents (11,4%) are disagree, 21 respondents (23,9%) are neutral, 30 respondents (34,1%) are agree, and 20 respondents (22,7%) are strongly agree about the statement. It can be concluded that by calculating the mean value, the brand recognition of TMO is 3,5 which is considered as High.

3. Brand Recall

From 88 respondents who are aware of TMO, 26 respondents (29,5%) are strongly disagree, 23 respondents (26,1%) are disagree, 20 respondents (22,7%) are neutral, 14 respondents (15,9%) are agree, and 5 respondents (5,7%) are strongly agree about the statement. It can be concluded that by calculating the mean value, the brand recall of TMO is 2,4 which is considered as Low.

4. Top of Mind

From 88 respondents who are aware of TMO, 19 respondents (21,6%) are strongly disagree, 15 respondents (17,0%) are disagree, 29 respondents (33,0%) are neutral, 14 respondents (15,9%) are agree, and 11 respondents (12,5%) are strongly agree about the statement. It can be concluded that by calculating the mean value, the top of mind of TMO is 2,8 which is considered as Moderate.

Recommendation Level and Priority

This section measures the willingness of respondents when it comes to recommend TMO as their preference for engine oil. From 88 respondents who are aware of TMO, 17 respondents (19,3%) are strongly disagree, 10 respondents (11,4%) are disagree, 29 respondents (33,0%) are neutral, 16 respondents (18,2%) are agree, and 16 respondents (18,2%) are strongly agree about the statement. It can be concluded that by calculating the mean value, the level recommendation of TMO is 3,0 which is considered as Moderate. Meanwhile for the variable priority, the questionnaire result is shown in Table 2 and for the preferences priority shown in Table 3.

Table 2. Priority of Variable

Attributes	Total Respondents							Total Score	Priority Result
	Rating Score	1 6	2 5	3 4	4 3	5 2	6 1		
Quality		154	21	33	3	17	27	1.231	1st
Price		71	73	61	18	16	16	1.137	2nd
Brand		50	81	68	15	24	17	1.087	3rd
Advertising		43	65	65	37	26	19	1.025	4th
Discount		57	51	61	39	27	20	1.032	5th
Packaging		44	62	56	37	26	30	991	6th

Table 3. Priority of Preferences

Attributes	Total Respondents							Total Score	Priority Result
	Rating Score	1 6	2 5	3 4	4 3	5 2	6 1		
Social Media		106	48	31	27	17	26	1.141	1st
Online Marketplace		90	46	45	33	24	17	1.114	2nd
Website		73	46	63	26	23	24	1.068	3rd
Billboard		58	52	68	48	9	20	1.062	4th
Television		65	49	57	37	32	15	1.053	5th
Radio		39	50	71	37	21	37	958	6th

BUSINESS SOLUTION

AIDA Framework

Based on the business issue of TMO, there are several marketing strategies that can be done by TAM in order to increase the brand awareness of TMO. The first strategy is AIDA Framework.

1. Attention

TMO can increase people's attention or awareness by being actively involved in digital marketing, creating the official website of TMO, and also collaborating with automotive influencers to promote TMO products. There are many platforms for digital marketing, for instance, Instagram. Currently, TAM already has an instagram account for TMO. However, TAM still does not utilize it as a main platform for their marketing activities or conduct any engagement with customers from that instagram account. In order to attract people's attention, TMO needs to create creative content and post it to their feeds or story on Instagram. Product photographs are just one aspect of this content, there are other elements that can add to its attractiveness. TMO needs to create material for feeds. This content need not always take the shape of product images, it might alternatively be an infographic or a slideshow with product knowledge. TMO also can create content for celebrating significant occasions, such as Eid, Christmas, Independence Day, and so on. There should be writing encouraging readers to use TMO goods at the end of the caption and do not forget about the hashtag of TMO which is popularly known as #TMOlebihpasticocok. The hashtag (#) can serve to increase the number of followers and the popularity of TMO. So, the more hashtags TMO uses, the more engagement TMO will get and the more popular it will.

2. Interest Once the TMO catch the people's attention, TMO needs to increase their interest by giving an Appealing Ads Gimmick in several media platforms, Official WhatsApp of TMO for facilitating customers who wants to get to know more about TMO products, and also giving Fun Fact about TMO or automotive matter in the TMO's social media. Verify that the content in TMO advertisement is organized, simple to read, and includes eye-catching subheadings and graphics. Concentrate on communicating only the most crucial message that TMO wishes to share with customers while keeping in mind what is most pertinent to TMO target market in regards to TMO products.

3. Desire

TMO can give promotion campaigns at any given time with various discount offers or different gamifications. The time or period of the campaign can also be equated with the celebration of big days in Indonesia. In addition, TMO must be able to offer solutions for customers who are looking for engine oil. TMO can provide a special application to help customers find TMO products that are suitable for their cars and available at which workshop. To increase customer desire, TMO must emphasize that they can provide solutions to customers' problems

4. Action

The author suggests that TMO provides a choice of various payment methods for customers who order through the application. For example, there are bank transfers, paylater, various e-cash options, and also the option of paying in stores. This makes it easier for customers who want to buy engine oil. In addition to ease of payment, TMO can also apply their previously running marketing program, namely the loyalty program in the form of point. By these features, TMO can encourage customers to take action towards TMO products by installing the application and purchasing TMO products.

Proposed STP

Figure 4. Proposed STP of TMO

Based on the results of previous interviews, the interviewee from the PT TAM's marketing team said that the positioning for the entire TMO product is Lebih Pasti Cocok untuk Toyota, while the positioning for each variant is still not there. In addition, for targeting, the source only mentioned the type of car classification without mentioning the year of the car's output. Therefore, the author in this session proposes the positioning and also the addition of the car year to the target to be more specific about the STP analysis of TMO.

CONCLUSION

The lubricant industry currently still has a fairly large market. This is in accordance with the growth in sales and the use of combustion engine cars. With a fairly large market, this makes the lubricant industry, especially car engine oil, have many players. Starting from local players to international players. One example is TMO. TMO is an oil distributed by PT Toyota Astra Motor (PT

TAM) that specially formulated for Toyota cars. The conditions that exist in the market, when discussing car oil changes, customer behaviour tends to prefer to buy car engine oil at an authorized workshop as well as change the oil at the venue. PT TAM, on the other hand, has actually carried out several marketing strategies to increase sales and awareness of PT TAM. Even though Toyota still lead 33,3% market share in Indonesia, the awareness is still low. This is reflected in the results of a questionnaire from the author which shows that 65.5% of the total 255 respondents do not know the TMO brand. In order to overcome this problem, the author suggest several marketing strategies such as rebuild TMO STP and formulate the marketing strategy based on AIDA Framework which consist of secure attention, evoke interest, stimulate desire, and initiate action towards TMO products from the customers. The author projected that by putting these ideas into practice, TMO's brand awareness would rise and that its digital marketing platform's customer engagement rate would rise.

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